

Reusable Workflows in Practice – a hands-on Workshop

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This full-day (8h) workshop is dedicated to research workflows and their reusability, providing an actionable contribution to the question of knowledge production addressed in the call for papers. In particular, we strive to foster community building around the recognition of the heuristic value of digital-based methodologies.

What we call a workflow is composed of descriptions of the work steps needed to implement a specific methodology in order to address a research question or provide guidance for analysis. While all research endeavours include workflows backing their methodology, not all of these can or should be made reusable. Yet when it comes to digital methods, their reusability can contribute significantly to not reinventing the wheel with each new project.

Workflows and their descriptions were first explored and implemented in the natural sciences, specifically in disciplines like bioinformatics, but their use is now spreading to other fields (Atkinson et al., 2017; Goble et al., 2020). The description of workflows in computer science is standardised with the Common Workflow Language (CWL) (Crusoe et al., 2022), which makes it readable by the human and the machine, describing the input, output, and parameters. In the Arts and Humanities, first efforts in standardisation work have been carried out (Riondet et al., 2018; Chagué et al., 2024) but there is at this point no formal unity and no publication culture in this area.

The goal of this workshop is to reflect on the reusability of digital-based research workflows relevant for Digital Humanities, and to contribute to the state of the art by testing existing workflows and producing new reusable descriptions. The workshop helps researchers improve their daily work by increasing awareness of their workflow practices, reducing duplicated effort, and providing hands-on guidance for creating clear, shareable, and citable workflows. It shows how standardised workflows boost efficiency, reproducibility, and long-term sustainability in DH research, and how they can be published as standalone contributions (e.g., in the DARIAH journal "Transformations") to increase visibility and credit. Participants also learn to contribute to and benefit from a wider ecosystem of reusable workflows that can accelerate future projects. The primary outlet for workflow descriptions is currently the SSH Open Marketplace, whose Editorial Board is contributing to improving access to reusable workflows (Barbot et al., 2024). The workflow "How to create a workflow in the SSH Open Marketplace?" is seminal in providing guidance and will serve as a basis for the second part of the workshop.

First part of the workshop (theory and critical analysis)

After an introduction round, the first 90mn slot will take place in the form of a world café with three different tables exploring the three following questions:

1. What is a workflow composed of?
2. Why are workflows important in research processes?
3. What does the reusability of a workflow consist in?

The output of the discussions will be integrated to a common pad and serve as a basis for the hands-on work that will follow for the rest of the day.

The second 90 minutes slot will be dedicated to the critical testing of workflows currently published on the SSH Open Marketplace. The moderators will help participants get acquainted with the description of the steps and the work environments required for their implementation. A focus will be on the workflows created in the context of the ATRIUM project: this research infrastructure-based EU project has the goal to make 20 workflows available until 2027. In order for these workflows to fulfill their function, they have to

be fully reusable. In this part of the workshop, the participants will test a selection of workflows concerning themselves with Automatic Text Recognition and Map Annotations as well as publishing Collections of Data. We will provide the workshop participants with criteria for assessing their reusability. We count a full 90 minutes for the implementation of the workflows and 30 minutes at the beginning of the afternoon session for feedback on the implementation.

This analysis will empower the participants with a sense of the pitfalls to avoid when writing their own workflows in the second part of the workshop.

Second part of the workshop (workflow creation)

In the second part of the workshop, participants will have the opportunity to write their own workflows. As mentioned, they will do this by leveraging the insights acquired during the first part, when testing existing workflows, and they will also consult the workflow "How to create a workflow in the SSH Open Marketplace?". The exercise will be carried out in groups, optimally with 3 people working on a single workflow, but different sizes of the groups will also be possible, depending on the participants' interests and experience.

Participants will consider their own research (or research they are familiar with) and will identify a part of their research processes that can be transformed into a reproducible workflow. On the one hand, this will entail recognising which methodologies can be reused in different projects and may benefit a wider community, and also how such methods might be generalised to accommodate an even broader range of scenarios and study cases. On the other hand, the participants will consider how such methodologies can be expressed as a series of individual, easily identifiable steps suitable to be performed multiple times in equal or similar conditions. If helpful, the participants can also outline a "demonstrator" as a companion to their workflow, i.e. an exemplary use case – with a specific dataset/research object – that shows how the workflow can be put into practice.

The participants will express their workflows mainly through verbal human-readable descriptions. In addition, they will have the opportunity to model the workflow according to a (semi-)formal language, if they already have prior experience with this, or by using a visual language, such as a simple diagram or sketch. They will express the goals of the workflow and identify any prior knowledge/skills required for its use. They will list requirements for its technical implementation, including which datasets, semantic artefacts, pieces of software, services etc. are needed. An important aspect will also be the description of the workflow with metadata, e.g. by assigning keywords from the TaDiRAH taxonomy (Borek et al., 2020) to different activities carried out in the workflow steps. To enhance interoperability and potential reuse, the participants will also

specify which data formats are required as input for the workflow, and which formats will be output at the end.

While not all the details of the final version of the workflows can be fleshed out in the course of an afternoon, the participants will in the end have an overall structure comprising the main components of their workflow as well as a draft of the content, possibly in a more fully-phrased form or in bullet points/short sentences. The draft workflow can be a first step towards actually publishing the workflow on the SSH Open Marketplace (SSHOMP). The workshop trainers, consisting of a team from the SSHOMP Editorial Board and the ATRIUM project, will be happy to assist the participants after the workshop to actually bring their workflows online. Experiences from the workshop "Erstellung von Workflows im SSH Open Marketplace" held at DHd2024 in Passau will be taken into account.

The last 30 minutes of the workshop will be dedicated to general feedback. The discussions carried out during the whole day as well as the feedback sessions might lead to the definition of possible criteria for the evaluation of workflows, the establishment of more specific guidelines related to particular disciplines or methodological perspectives, or any other aspect raised by the participants.

General information

The workshop is a combination of a training event and a collaborative form of work on the topic of research reproducibility and workflows.

The workshop is directed at a wide audience, comprising researchers, technicians, and more generally people involved in research and infrastructure, with a specific focus on open science, interoperability and research reproducibility.

Participants are limited to 15 people, each should bring their own computers and have access to the internet. The room should be equipped with a beamer as well as A2 white sheets of paper and color markers for the world café (paper table cloth would also work). Participants should be willing to engage in writing a workflow, e.g. have identified a portion of their research pipeline they would like to formalise during the workshop and eventually publish on the SSH Open Marketplace.

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